

Exploring the Fit: Analysing Material Selection for Interactive Markers in MAR Games through Co-Design

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Fig. 1: From left to right, participants are shown creating markers. In Workshop 1 (left), participants used whiteboards to recreate markers from an existing MAR game. In Workshop 2 (right), participants used foam blocks to create their own markers. The image highlights the exploration of different materials in the two workshops.

Abstract

Understanding how different user groups interact and perceive material selection for interactive markers in mobile augmented reality (MAR) games is essential for effective design. This study uses a qualitative approach, incorporating interviews and workshops to examine the preferences and behaviours of designers (N=6) and children (N=8). Designers highlighted the importance of using versatile and environmentally sustainable materials that can be customised for various games. Meanwhile, children's interactions with these materials revealed challenges such as decision-making pressure and reliance on peer collaboration to navigate unfamiliar materials. The study identified five critical considerations for selecting materials: simplification, customisation, sustainability, balanced creativity, and collaboration. Our results show that while designers prioritise creative potential, user engagement is influenced by material ease and collaboration. This study provides key insights into the design

considerations for MAR games, suggesting aligning designer expectations with actual user behaviour for creating successful and immersive MAR experiences.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Participatory design; Mixed / augmented reality.**

Keywords

Qualitative Study, Tangible Markers, Mobile Augmented Reality

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1 Introduction

Augmented reality (AR) has become a compelling technology in digital entertainment, seamlessly merging the virtual and physical worlds [16]. The unique characteristic of AR is the augmentation

of the real world with computerised information instead of reconstructing it entirely in a virtual environment. AR applications have evolved to be utilised in various fields, such as education [75], healthcare [21], engineering [9], and gaming [27]. The importance of AR games for players highlights the role of imagination and social interaction [37]. It delves into the importance of player imagination and social relationships in enhancing the gameplay experience, suggesting that AR games can support human imagination without replacing it [37]. Furthermore, we can observe the development and diverse applications of AR games, showcasing their potential in education [60], entertainment [3], mental state examination [23], and immersive gaming experiences [36] both indoors and outdoors. Among the many augmented reality games, one domain that has particularly attracted attention is mobile gaming.

Mobile augmented reality (MAR) has made AR technology easily accessible to the general public through smartphones [18], increasing its adoption that broadens its impact beyond traditional gaming experiences [13]. Through pairwise interactions in AR games, players interact via smartphones in an AR space, highlighting the development of AR technology in gaming experiences towards interactive and engaging gameplay scenarios [56]. The applications of AR leverage a range of tracking techniques, including sensor-based, vision-based (marker-based and markerless), and hybrid methods, to achieve accurate and robust tracking [12, 34, 51, 73]. Additionally, there is an increasing focus on the adoption and importance of location-based [32, 53] and marker-based [31] features in AR. Location-based AR uses GPS data to place virtual objects in specific real-world locations, allowing players to interact with their environment dynamically. Popularised by the success of Niantic's Pokémon Go [1] in 2016, location-based mobile augmented reality (MAR) has since been featured in numerous other publications [17, 22, 58] to name a few. Marker-based AR, however, relies on visual markers, like images or codes, to trigger the appearance of digital content when scanned by the device. The usability in marker design and implementation can directly influence user motivation and learning effectiveness [19]. Tangible markers enhance engagement by providing sensory-rich, hands-on interactions that bridge the physical and digital worlds, fostering deeper user involvement and creativity [42]. Furthermore, mobile AR games are effective in education, engaging students with interactive, immersive experiences that boost learning and retention [77]. Using tangible markers in collaborative tasks can promote peer interaction and collective problem-solving, making them effective tools for inducing teamwork and social connection in educational and gaming environments [39]. Social-emotional learning (SEL) enhances youth development by improving interpersonal skills, emotional regulation, and overall well-being, fostering positive attitudes and behaviours that support academic and social success [66]. Additionally, online communication tools (OCTs) facilitate peer connections and social interaction among adolescents by bridging physical and digital spaces, enabling meaningful relationships in both virtual and real-world contexts [47]. Mobile AR games also promote social connections and help create a more inclusive environment, particularly for early adolescents [46]. Collaboration fosters social connection, and tangible markers facilitate collaboration. Therefore, tangible markers can play a role in promoting social connection. By integrating interactive markers into gameplay, mobile AR games can

provide dynamic opportunities for adolescents to strengthen social-emotional skills and build meaningful connections with others. This study highlights the importance of bridging the gap between designer expectations and user preferences in material selection for MAR games. Our qualitative analysis of designer interviews and children's workshops revealed five critical factors influencing material selection: simplification, customisation, sustainability, balanced creativity, and collaboration.

To the best of our knowledge, current literature reveals a clear gap in using interactive markers in MAR games for children. This paper presents an early study focused on children's interactions with different materials for interactive markers in MAR games. Specifically, we investigate the following research questions (RQs):

- RQ1: What are the key considerations for designers when selecting materials for interactive markers in MAR games?
- RQ2: What types of interactions do children exhibit with various interactive marker materials, and how do these interactions differ?
- RQ3: How do designers' expectations of effective marker materials compare to the actual preferences and behaviours of children?

Understanding how children interact with different materials can help designers create more engaging and intuitive MAR experiences. Unlike purely digital features, tangible markers in AR are particularly deserving of further investigation because they bridge the gap between the physical and virtual worlds, fostering hands-on, sensory-rich learning experiences. The promotion of hands-on learning through modularity encourages creativity, problem-solving, and fine motor skill development [61, 68]. By reusing materials commonly found in classrooms, such as toys, tangible markers can make AR solutions more sustainable and adaptable to diverse educational contexts. Moreover, exploring diverse materials can enhance the versatility of these markers by leveraging material properties to support scalable complexity, thereby catering to a wider range of age groups and skill levels. The disconnect between the effectiveness of AR technology and its implementation in classrooms highlights the need for more comprehensive research that addresses these barriers and promotes effective integration strategies [43]. Different material choices could promote deeper educational engagement and creativity, addressing gaps in existing commercial solutions like OSMO [50] and paving the way for more flexible and inclusive AR learning tools. By exploring the gap between designers' expectations and children's actual preferences, this study contributes to improving the design process for MAR games, particularly in educational and entertainment settings. These insights are crucial for designers looking to enhance user engagement, improve learning outcomes, foster creativity and social interaction among young players. This study emphasises the importance of thoughtful material design that balances creativity, usability, and sustainability. By simplifying choices, enhancing customisation, promoting sustainability, encouraging creativity, and fostering collaboration, the right materials can significantly improve engagement and social interaction in MAR games. Ultimately, this research addresses a key challenge in the growing field of AR, offering practical suggestions for designing effective and child-friendly AR experiences.

Fig. 2: The visual illustrates the co-design process, which began with a designer interview focused on brainstorming various marker materials for mobile AR games. In Workshop 1, children played a mobile AR game to learn AR concepts and markers, while Workshop 2 had them explore materials to create their own markers.

2 Related Work

This section explores how marker-based AR enhances MAR gameplay, bridging the digital and physical worlds to boost engagement and immersion. By examining trends, we highlight interactive markers' role in fostering meaningful experiences, well-being, and social connection, leading to a deeper investigation into marker material design.

2.1 Mobile Augmented Reality Games

Mobile augmented reality (MAR) games have evolved using handheld devices like smartphones and tablets to create interactive and engaging gaming experiences. The advancements in handheld augmented reality (HAR) highlight the processing power and sensors that have made it suitable for AR systems. Advancements in handheld devices' processing power and sensors have enhanced user interactions and led to innovative gameplay concepts in MAR applications. Through their study, Lehto et al. [41] encouraged players to explore different locations through playful interactions with historical characters, creating an immersive experience that connects users to cultural heritage. The game's location-based elements foster engagement and curiosity, allowing visitors to learn about history interactively. Similarly, Ekonomou et al. [17] employed mobile AR to enhance the educational experience of secondary school students visiting the Delphi archaeological site. The app provides location-aware interactions that allow students to engage with the site playfully, learning about important monuments and their histories. The use of MAR in this context bridges formal and informal learning, fostering greater student participation and cultivating various skills. Xue et al. [10] explained using AR to create an interactive learning environment for preschool children. The AR tools allow children to observe virtual objects superimposed on real-world scenes captured via a video camera. This setup enables children to interact with virtual elements by manipulating physical objects, enhancing their vocabulary, and learning more engagingly and intuitively.

Furthermore, three publications [5, 25, 42] also highlight location-based and marker-based augmentation techniques, allowing virtual content to be anchored to specific geographical locations and physical markers within the environment. Understanding the value of different types of augmentation in MAR games is crucial for selecting interactive markers that enhance engagement and learning. By leveraging the unique strengths of location-based and marker-based augmentation, designers can create immersive experiences that connect virtual content to meaningful real-world contexts. This ensures the selected markers align with the game's objectives and offer contextually relevant, dynamic interactions tailored to the learner's environment, making the educational experience more engaging and impactful. This directly informs RQ1 by providing insights into the key considerations designers must address when selecting marker materials, such as usability, alignment with game objectives, and the potential to create immersive and meaningful interactions.

2.2 Role of Markers

Markers in MAR games serve as physical or digital reference points that trigger and anchor virtual content within the real world, creating a seamless blend of reality and augmented elements. By scanning these markers, players can unlock interactive experiences, access educational content, or engage with game mechanics directly tied to specific locations or objects. Rachman et al. [52] discuss using 2D card markers in an AR fighting game. These markers are essential for detecting the location and orientation of virtual objects, allowing for interactive gameplay. The value of markers in this context is crucial, enabling a more immersive and engaging gaming experience.

Moreover, Syamsudin et al. [65] mention using markers to create interactive educational experiences. The value of markers is in their ability to enhance student engagement and interaction with educational content, making learning more effective and enjoyable. Buhion et al. [8] highlighted the functional importance of markers in MAR research by comparing the capabilities of 2D and 3D markers. They argued that 2D markers, often printable, offer greater flexibility in scaling and interaction, making them easily accessible and adaptable for various gaming scenarios. On the other hand, 3D markers, which involve physical objects, provide a more immersive user experience by integrating tangible elements into the gameplay. This distinction suggests that future research could strategically explore the use of tangible markers, particularly 3D markers, to further enhance the immersion and interactivity of AR experiences, aligning marker choice with specific user experience goals. Li et al. [42] discussed various interaction techniques, including tangible interactions that could involve markers. The value of using markers is highlighted in their potential to create more intuitive and engaging interactions for children, enhancing the overall gaming experience and learning outcomes.

Building on this work, RQ1 aims to explore the potential of tangible markers to expand the possibilities of MAR games, focusing on how physical interaction with markers can lead to more immersive educational experiences. By investigating how different types of markers—both 2D and 3D—impact player engagement and learning, we seek to provide valuable insights into designing more interactive and effective MAR applications. This study will contribute to

understanding how tangible markers can enhance gameplay and create more meaningful interactions, particularly for educational and entertainment purposes.

2.3 Social Connection

Traditional social skill training (SST) and social and emotional learning (SEL) programs have been widely recognised for their effectiveness in enhancing adolescents' social-emotional skills and overall well-being. Taylor et al. [66] present a meta-analysis of 82 school-based social and emotional learning (SEL) interventions involving over 97,000 students. The analysis demonstrates that SEL programs enhance positive youth development by improving social-emotional skills, attitudes, and well-being indicators. Moreover, Mittmann et al. [47] explore the influence of online communication tools (OCTs) on friendships among early adolescents. The study identifies key themes such as the value of phones, OCTs and the fusion of online and offline interactions. The findings suggest that OCTs enhance peer connectedness and social interactions during early adolescence. Thus, integrating social connection and MAR games can create dynamic opportunities for adolescents to develop and strengthen social-emotional skills, fostering meaningful interactions and deeper connections in virtual and real-world environments.

Mittmann et al. [46] study focuses on social interaction and mental health; AR technology implies the potential for markers to facilitate engagement and interaction among players. The value of markers in this context lies in their ability to create shared immersive experiences that promote real-world social connections and a sense of belonging among early adolescents. Further, Chen et al. [14] advanced the field of marker-based MAR games by introducing stacking transparent AR interactive markers. This approach represents a considerable leap in the complexity and interactivity of such games, allowing for novel inputs and more intricate interactions. In their study, the stacking mechanics can be used to generate creative outputs like musical compositions, thereby enhancing the creative potential of users. This innovation also promotes social interaction by encouraging collaborative gameplay and shared experiences. Therefore, interactive markers-based games can unlock new opportunities for implementing interventions that foster social connection among players by enabling shared interactions, collaborative challenges, and collective creativity within augmented realities. RQ2 contributes to this focus by examining how children interact with different marker materials, shedding light on the types of social connections and collaborative behaviours these materials foster during gameplay.

While previous studies have extensively explored MAR's potential in enhancing education, entertainment, and social connectedness, using physical interactive markers, particularly in children's gameplay, remains underexplored. This paper aims to fill this gap by providing empirical insights into how children engage with different marker materials and how these interactions align with or differ from designer expectations by answering RQ3. By investigating the selection and design considerations of marker materials from a designer's perspective, the study not only contributes to the existing body of knowledge but also paves the way for further research into the application of 3D tangible markers.

3 Methodology

Co-design is a collaborative, creative process that combines diverse participants in a shared inquiry and imaginative exploration to develop ideas and solutions collectively [49]. Co-design carries ethical dimensions, as it involves participants sharing experiences, empathising with one another, and collaboratively identifying problems and co-creating solutions [64]. The co-design process often involves multiple iterations, allowing for continuous feedback and refinement of the design (see [24, 45, 63, 69]). It empowers users by giving them a voice in the development of solutions that affect their lives [30] and enhances the overall quality of the design by incorporating diverse perspectives and insights from users [28, 35, 59, 74]. Moreover, co-design helps to ensure that the developed interventions are not only user-friendly but also contextually relevant. This alignment can improve the overall effectiveness of the intervention [4, 28, 54].

In this study, we consulted with the first target group (designers) to address RQ1 and co-designed with the second target group (children) to address RQ2. For RQ1, we consulted with designers to brainstorm the process of analysing material selection for interactive markers in MAR games, ensuring their expertise informed the creative solutions. The designers brought their technical knowledge and creative insights into the process, helping to shape the material choices in a way that aligned with design principles and game functionality. For RQ2, we worked with children, engaging them in the co-design process to explore their perspectives and preferences regarding material choices. Additionally, as a part of RQ2 we aimed to understand the types of social connections and collaborative behaviours these materials foster during gameplay, providing insights into how tangible markers support peer interaction and teamwork. The children's participation allowed us to gather valuable insights about how the end-users (i.e. the children), experience and interact with different materials. For RQ3, we explored how designers' expectations of effective marker materials compared to children's actual preferences and behaviours. This inquiry allowed us to bridge the gap between expert assumptions and real-world usage by children. By involving designers as consultants and children as co-researchers, we could effectively apply co-design methods to gather insights and draw conclusions from each target group's unique perspectives (see Figure 2). This multi-layered approach enriched our understanding of material selection in MAR games and facilitated the creation of technically sound and user-friendly solutions.

3.1 Interview

Based on Ritter and Mostert [55], we conducted an online brainstorming interview with designers using three distinct idea-generation techniques: Silence, Lines of Evolution, and Random Connections. By incorporating these methods, we aimed to enhance creativity and innovation, leveraging varied approaches to stimulate professional collaboration.

3.1.1 Participants. The study with the first target group (designers (N=6)) was conducted through an online interview in March 2024 within a time slot of one and a half hours. Table 1 provides basic information about their specialisation, industry experiences, AR design experiences, and MAR game-playing experience that helps to

understand participants' backgrounds and the overall composition of the sample. The final six participants were selected based on the following criteria: 1) a designer with a minimum of 5 years of work experience in the digital design space, 2) a designer with experience designing projects for AR, virtual reality (VR) or mixed reality (XR), and 3) a designer who has at least played one MAR game. To proceed with the study, the designers signed a consent form.

3.1.2 Material and Stimuli. The online interview with the designers did not require any specific materials, though participants were informed they could use paper, stationery, or any design software to aid in brainstorming. While two participants chose to use pen and paper during the session in order to organise their ideas, this was solely for their personal reference and to support their visual thinking process.

3.1.3 Procedure. One of the co-authors conducted the online brainstorming interview with the designers, structured into three stages: introduction and context setting, discussions on experiences with AR and MAR, and brainstorming for marker materials. The interview format was as follows:

- (1) Introduction and context building: The facilitator introduced themselves and outlined the interview's purpose and the brainstorming session's structure setting the tone for the session.
- (2) Experiences with AR and MAR: Participants were invited to share their experiences with AR technology, including their work in AR, gaming, and familiarity with MAR games.
- (3) Brainstorming: Designers brainstormed marker materials using three techniques: random connection, where participants linked unrelated items; silence, allowing free idea generation; and reflection, exploring how existing ideas could evolve.

3.2 Workshops

Based on Andersen and Wakkary [2], we conducted two "magic machine" workshops with children, focusing on MAR games. As a speculative design approach, magic machine workshops seek to empower participants by shifting leadership of the creative process to them. These workshops place users in "magical" scenarios, moving beyond technology tied to existing artefacts. This approach removes the constraints of conventional systems, allowing participants to explore and express their ideas freely and without limitation.

3.2.1 Participants. The study with the second target group (children (N=8)) was conducted through two magic machines workshop sessions. While this study does not intend to be representative nor exhaustive in the sampling, Table 1 displays basic demographic information such as gender, grade, experience with AR and their experiences playing MAR games. All participants were recruited with the help of a selected grammar school in the Czech Republic with the assistance of a local school psychologist. The following criteria were set for selection: 1) The participant is in 7th grade (between the ages of 10-14 years) of the grammar school and 2) The participant has a communicative level of English language.

The workshops with children were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Masaryk University, and all volunteers agreed to participate, and their legal representatives signed an informed

consent. Participation in the interviews and workshops was entirely voluntary, and each participant had the right to withdraw at any time.

3.2.2 Material and Stimuli. Workshop 1 utilised Google Pixel 7 mobile phones and headphones which were provided by the facilitators to play the AR game. Art supplies such as black pens and A4-sized whiteboards were used for the creative session. Additional notepads, paper, and pens were available for the participants to aid their engagement and note-taking. For the purposes of a gameplay session in Workshop 1, MAR game called LINA [46] was used. LINA is designed for early adolescents to enhance peer interaction and foster a sense of belonging while addressing mental health issues.

Workshop 2 was a follow up of Workshop 1 session which also incorporated art supplies for the creative session, including black pens and A4-sized whiteboards, along with notepads and pens for the children. Statler et al. [67] explore the relationship between materials, emotions, and learning in their study. The authors argue that emotional engagement enhances learning effectiveness and that the choice of materials can influence engagement. Key characteristics of materials, such as fluidity, resistivity, ambiguity of form, boundaries, quantity, mediation, kinesthetics, and sensory awareness, are discussed as factors that can influence emotional engagement and learning outcomes. Cetin et al. [78] suggest that drawings effectively communicate life events and experiences, offering valuable insights into children's emotions and social dynamics. Based on this, we chose whiteboards and markers as the first material for marker creation. Franklin et al. [20] explore the effectiveness of using games and puzzles to promote active learning, enhance student engagement, and encourage peer-assisted learning. Consequently, we selected puzzle pieces as the second material, allowing participants to engage with them as both 2D and 3D objects, further encouraging creative freedom. LeGoff [39] proposed using LEGO® to facilitate social interaction and boost children's motivation for social learning. We incorporated LEGO® as the third material to foster a sense of familiarity among participants, encouraging them to construct complex objects based on their prior experience with the material. Lastly, Zuo et al. [76] examined the impact of different textures on user comfort and emotional response, highlighting the importance of sensory properties in material selection to optimise user experience. In light of this, we introduced foam blocks as the final marker material, offering participants a distinct tactile experience compared to LEGO® and puzzle pieces.

Both Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 were performed in a local grammar school in spacious lecture rooms providing a quiet and undisturbed place.

3.2.3 Procedure. Three co-authors facilitated the workshops, with two local facilitators aiding engagement in English sessions. A school psychologist ensured children's well-being. The three co-authors assisted with logistics throughout both workshops, took reflexive notes and asked additional questions during the feedback sessions. Across two workshops, participants created 48 marker prototypes through a structured five-stage process (see Figure 3).

The format for Workshop 1 was as follows:

- (1) Introduction and Ice-Breaking Activity: The three facilitators introduced themselves and gave a brief overview of AR

Designers				
ID	Occupation	Work Experience	Design for AR	Mobile AR Games
1	Illustrator	5 years	Designed few projects for XR	Played few games
2	Communication Designer	8 years	Designed few projects for AR	Only played Pokemon Go
3	Typographer	6 years	Designed graphics for AR	Played one
4	UX Designer	8 years	Designed graphics for AR	Only played Pokemon Go
5	Tattoo artist	10 years	Designed two projects for XR	Played few games
6	Animator	8 years	Designed for VR	Played 2-3 games
Children				
ID	Grade	Gender	Experience with AR	Mobile AR Games
7	7th	Female	Heard about AR	None
8	7th	Female	Heard about AR	None
9	7th	Male	Knows about AR	Only played Pokemon Go
10	7th	Female	Knows about VR	None
11	7th	Female	None	None
12	7th	Male	Heard about AR	None
13	7th	Female	None	None
14	7th	Female	Knows about VR	None

Table 1: The table provides data collected from interviews and workshops with designers and children. It outlines their basic information and highlights their experience and familiarity with AR technology.

Fig. 3: The comparison between Workshops 1 and 2, with differences emphasised in blue. Session 1 highlighted differences in gameplay and story creation, while Session 2 saw Workshop 1 participants recreating markers and Workshop 2 participants designing their own, shifting from replication to creation.

games. As a ice-breaking activity, participants were asked to briefly introduce themselves and describe their hobbies to the group.

- (2) Session 1: Gameplay Session: Facilitators began by discussing AR familiarity, revealing most participants were unaware of AR, with only one having prior experience. A facilitator then explained AR game principles using the LINA prototype, demonstrating spatial scanning, markers, and QR code parallels. Participants received phones with the LINA prototype

and played while facilitators observed and provided support as needed.

- (3) Feedback Collection: Participants completed an online survey on mobile phones.
- (4) Session 2: Creative Session: Facilitators presented two LINA game markers, tasking participants with reimagining and recreating them freely using whiteboards and markers.
- (5) Feedback Collection: After creating the prototypes, the facilitators asked the participants to present their prototypes to the group and explain their thought processes behind them. Participants were asked to answer the questions from the facilitators and other participants. Participants were not informed about the discussion beforehand, as Andersen [2] highlights that this step is a vital aspect of the magic machines method. Each participant presented their creation to the group and provided feedback through group discussion.

The format for Workshop 2 was as follows:

- (1) Introduction and ice-breaking activity: The three facilitators re-introduced themselves and familiarised the participants with the main aims of the workshop. As an ice-breaking activity, participants were invited to share a highlight from their past week with the rest of the group. The facilitators began by revisiting the context of the first workshop, held three weeks prior.
- (2) Session 1: Story Generation: Once the participants were aligned with the context, they were randomly divided into pairs to engage in a creative activity. A total of four groups participated, with each group provided with a whiteboard and a black marker to begin the session. Each pair was tasked with creating a story by using eight objects as part of the narrative.
- (3) Feedback collection: Presentation of stories. Once the stories were completed, each group was invited to present their narrative and the eight objects they had incorporated. After all the presentations, the participants were asked to vote

for a story they wished to process for the next part of the workshop.

- (4) Session 2: Marker creation. For the marker creation activity, participants were asked to leave their groups and work individually. The story that received the most votes was selected, and one facilitator wrote the eight objects from the story onto individual pieces of paper, distributing them randomly among the participants. The participants were instructed that various materials would be provided and that they had 10 minutes to create the assigned object. Participants were provided different types of materials in the following order: pens and whiteboards, coloured puzzle pieces, LEGO® bricks and foam blocks. The facilitators took observations notes throughout the session.
- (5) Feedback collection: The feedback collection process involved two stages. First, participants described their prototypes during the creative session, offering insights into their thought process. Second, the participants completed an online survey to share feedback about their experiences.

3.2.4 Rationale for Workshop Protocol Differences. Saiger et al. [57] states that children and young people tend to show greater engagement and achieve better results when they have a clear understanding of the context, subject matter, design process, methods, tools, and technologies being used. Therefore, the intention of Workshop 1 was to introduce and familiarise the children with the concept of AR through an interactive experience. We achieved this by having them play LINA [46] a MAR game designed for early adolescents. The goal was to help participants grasp key AR concepts like spatial recognition and the role of markers. To reinforce this, children re-drew game markers on whiteboards, engaging creatively with the material (see Figure 3). Workshop 2 built on this foundation, starting with children creating personalised storylines to set the context for the design task. They then used four materials to create markers, applying insights from Workshop 1 to deepen their understanding and creativity. Separating the activities into two workshops allowed time for learning and familiarisation with AR concepts. Workshop 2 employed a low-fidelity participatory design method, which was cost-effective, there was the ease of access to materials, and provided the ability to design for technologies that are either not currently available or do not yet exist [11]. Another study suggests that low-fidelity prototypes often encourage children to provide honest feedback and focus on functionality rather than aesthetic appeal leading to more constructive criticism of design flaws [62]. By structuring the activities into two workshops, we were able to guide the children from foundational understanding to active design participation, fostering both their comprehension and engagement with AR.

3.3 Data Analysis

We conducted qualitative data analysis for both the interviews and workshops using Glaser et al.'s [26] approach. The interviews with designers explored material selection, while the workshops with children focused on their interactions with selected materials. This allowed us to achieve our goal of generating novel theoretical insights rooted in empirical data, as it prioritises data-driven exploration.

The first author conducted and audio-recorded interviews with the designers, which were later transcribed. Observation notes were also taken throughout the interview process. The transcripts were analysed using the thematic analysis approach of Braun et al.'s [6, 7]. Based on the insights gathered from the interview, the four materials were selected for workshops with the children. Both workshops were audio-recorded and transcribed by the first and third authors, while all three authors took observation notes during the sessions.

The workshop transcriptions were analysed similarly to the designer interviews, following thematic analysis with different coding strategies. We systematically analysed the qualitative data through the stages of transcription, data organisation, familiarisation, coding, theme identification, recoding, and category development [38]. Two authors independently transcribed the audio recordings. The first three authors then reviewed the transcripts, field observation notes, and photographs from the workshops to familiarise themselves with the data, taking observation notes. In the first round, two authors analysed the transcripts from the two workshops to establish preliminary categories using open coding. This approach enabled the authors to identify categories representing patterns or ideas within the data. In the second round, the first author revisited the initial themes aligning them with the theoretical concept of the learning journey [71]. By revisiting the data, the first author refined the codes and categories. Using the learning journey framework, the initial categories were aligned with specific themes: the first category, "initial struggle and adaptability of materials," was associated with the learning and change theme; the second category, "decision-making pressure and creativity in prototypes," was linked to the continuity and discontinuity theme; and the third category, "collaboration and peer learning," directly corresponded to the collaboration theme. The process of exploring relationships between categories and testing emerging theories against the data ensured they are grounded in the findings. These analyses were shared among all three authors, leading to the refinement of three final categories that directly addressed the research question. The analysis is supported by participant quotes and explanations of their creative outputs.

4 Results

The results highlight designers' preference for recyclable materials balancing function and creativity, while children faced challenges with adaptability and collaboration. Findings underscore aligning material choices with user needs. The next section further analyses designer perspectives, child interactions, and marker feasibility.

4.1 Designer Interviews: Material Selection

The exploration of material selection for interactive markers that the designers presented revealed a complex interplay between functionality and user engagement. The participants mainly emphasised the need for materials that enhance technical performance and creative potential. This exploration of the interplay between functionality and user engagement reflects participants' perceived emphasis on marker selection in general. Discussions among designers revealed an evolution in their brainstorming process, shifting

from basic, familiar tools like pen and paper to more complex and inventive materials.

4.1.1 Use of Everyday and Recyclable Materials. Designers showed three abstract ideas for turning to every day and recyclable materials when creating markers for AR due to their simplicity and ease of availability. They all discussed using pen and paper, which is commonly found and easily available. ID3 further emphasised that the paper can be easily cut into various shapes and sizes to form interactive markers and can be rearranged to fit different scenarios. ID5 stated that this approach not only makes use of readily available materials but also allows for quick and cost-effective experimentation. ID4 expressed *although pen and paper are easily available I think whiteboards and markers are better considering they are recyclable.*

Some more creative ideas by participants involved using items like sea shells and dice, which also offer unique textures and aesthetic qualities that can enhance the AR experience. Sea shells, for example, can be used to create markers with natural patterns and colours, adding an organic touch to the digital interaction. Similarly, three participants explained that dice could be assembled into custom markers with various shapes and colour combinations. ID6 noted that using such items contributes to environmental sustainability and provides a distinct visual appeal that makes markers stand out. These approaches reflect a thoughtful consideration of cost-effectiveness and creative expression, leveraging everyday materials to create engaging AR experiences.

4.1.2 Versatility and Customisation of Physical Objects. Participants valued the versatility and customisation offered by physical objects when selecting markers for mobile AR experiences. For them, versatile materials balance creative potential with practical considerations to achieve engagement. Five participants discussed the key factor of flexibility in creating dynamic markers tailored to any game, scenario, or interactive experience. Participants discussed how LEGO® bricks and clay can be easily moulded into various shapes and structures. ID4 felt that LEGO®'s modular nature supports collaborative play, where users can build and modify markers together. Participants' perception of using puzzle pieces was considered creative material with tremendous potential. ID5 and ID6 felt that 3D wooden models could be assembled into markers that challenged players and engaged them in problem-solving activities. ID5 recalled *I remember as a child I used to play with 3D wooden puzzles. I even made a bike from it. Materials like these can really inspire children to explore complex objects.*

On the other hand, four participants discussed how clay offered a unique and malleable medium. ID2 felt that clay can enable intricate designs that can enhance visual appeal. In addition, three participants discussed quicksand to be seen as creative material with immense potential.

Despite the creative advantages of these materials, participants were also mindful of the practical challenges they present. For example, while clay offers a high degree of customisation, it can be difficult to ensure consistent marker recognition due to its variability and the potential for surface imperfections. Similarly, while quicksand allows for innovative marker creation, its use in AR applications may be limited by difficulties in reliably scanning and detecting the markers.

4.1.3 Importance of Colour and Patterns. Colour and patterns were key considerations for all the participants. They expressed that vibrant colours and intricate patterns could enhance marker visibility and increase user engagement. Participants referred to colourful materials as mosaic patterns, which could create visually striking markers that could be easily distinguished from their surroundings. ID1 highlighted *mosaic patterns are so visually complex that they could be used as interactive markers. They can capture attention and possibly make the AR experience more immersive.*

Colorful 2D and 3D shapes are another popular choice among participants. These shapes are aesthetically pleasing and could serve practical functions by making markers stand out. The participants stated that incorporating geometric patterns and contrasting hues could ensure that the markers remained prominent and engaging, even in varied environmental conditions. This approach could help to maintain user interest and interaction throughout the MAR experience. ID6 felt that using high-contrast colours like black and white or complementary colour pairs ensures that markers are visible and easily distinguishable.

4.2 Children Workshops: Material Interaction

In the first workshop, participants experienced playing a Mobile AR game for the first time. The primary objective was to familiarise them with AR gaming, ensuring their input in the follow-up workshop was more qualitative. Participants generally enjoyed their first encounter with MAR gaming. Seven out of eight participants highlighted difficulties in understanding the AR features, such as scanning the floor to find objects, which required assistance from either facilitators or peers. Similarly, five participants initially struggled with scanning the correct image markers, often attempting to scan unrelated physical items like bags or books in the classroom. Observing the other participants helped those who were struggling to understand the process. However, one participant, unable to successfully scan an image marker independently, requested assistance from a facilitator. The participants appreciated the physical engagement of walking while playing the game. For example, they noted:

I liked the way some things were supposed to appear on the floor. (ID7)

I liked the marker with the raincoat. It was aesthetically pleasing. But I was sad that I couldn't see the objects which were supposed to appear on the floor. I have a feeling I would love that. (ID13).

Seven out of eight participants agreed that AR enhanced their gaming experience and wanted to continue playing the game. Their enthusiasm stemmed from their fascination with AR and the combination of physical movement and interaction with the digital world. ID12 expressed *I had never imagined a mobile game that also has physical activity and movement with the real world.*

In the second part of the workshop, facilitators randomly presented two markers (raincoat and diary) from the LINA game for participants to reimagine and recreate each marker using their own creativity. Six of eight participants created a simplified version of the 'raincoat' marker, appreciating its straightforward design (see Figure 4, left). This indicated a preference for simplicity in their creations. In contrast, the "diary" marker inspired more diverse

and imaginative interpretations. While three participants created a symbolic representation in the form of a pen, two participants designed a lock, and the remaining three crafted an open book (see Figure 4, right). In particular, five participants chose to think more abstractly, using metaphorical representations rather than literal recreations. This shift from direct representation in the first marker to metaphorical thinking in the second highlights the evolving approach of the participants to creativity and interpretation.

In the follow-up workshop 2, participants were encouraged to develop stories using eight objects. The stories created by the groups included:

- (1) A detective story about finding a lost friend
- (2) A journey to help a bullied friend
- (3) Befriending animals in a forest
- (4) Re-connecting with lost friends through shared activities

After presenting their ideas, the participants voted to work with story no 4. Six out of eight participants preferred this story, as they felt it reflected how activities make interacting and building connections easier. Building on these insights, one of the facilitators prepared eight pieces of paper, each labelled with the name of one object from the stories created earlier, and distributed them randomly among the participants. We now reflect on children's interactions with new materials through the lens of the strategies they developed to navigate challenges and decisions. These categories emerged as participants adapted to unfamiliar tools, managed the pressure of decision-making, collaborated with peers, and expressed material preferences. Our focus was not to classify participants by strategy but to uncover insights from their creative processes and interactions. Some participants exhibited multiple strategies, reflecting the complexity of their experiences. The four main strategies are listed and described in detail in the following subsections.

4.2.1 Struggle with New Materials. When introduced to unfamiliar materials such as puzzle pieces and foam blocks in Workshop 2, the participants exhibited noticeable confusion and uncertainty, reflecting a common struggle when adapting to new tools. The puzzle pieces, which were entirely new to the participants, posed an initial challenge. All eight participants showed signs of hesitation and confusion as they attempted to figure out how to use these uniquely shaped pieces to create objects. The student's initial reactions were marked by uncertainty, a natural response when faced with the unknown, and this was universally observed across the group. The facilitators observed the participants' interactions with the new materials but did not directly assist or support them during their initial exploration and adaptation. While the facilitators were present and available to help if needed, none of the participants requested assistance.

Despite the initial struggle, the participants quickly transitioned from confusion to experimentation. For example, they stated:

Making things from puzzles was so confusing in the beginning. I didn't know what to do. I had never played with puzzles before, but when I figured it out, it was so much fun that remade my object again. (ID8)

I created the mobile phone twice after I understood how to play with the foam thing. (ID12)

I did not know what I wanted to do with the puzzles, so I kept playing with them to figure it out. Then, I suddenly got comfortable and made a 2D and a 3D book. (ID10)

This approach allowed facilitators to observe genuine problem-solving as participants learned to work with unfamiliar materials. Participants were willing to experiment creatively with different materials in Workshop 2, often restarting their projects once they became more comfortable with the medium. 62.5 % of the participants (five out of eight) restarted their objects after initial trials, showcasing their adaptability and desire for creative experimentation.

With puzzle pieces, five participants restarted their objects after using the material, indicating a learning curve and adaptability. Among the eight participants, three managed to create 2D objects, another two successfully built 3D structures, and the remaining three experimented with a combination of 2D and 3D forms. The distribution of the types of objects created—2D, 3D, and mixed—demonstrates the diverse ways participants can engage with new materials once they understand their potential applications.

A similar pattern of quick adaptation emerged with foam blocks. Six of the eight participants completed their markers in less than four minutes. 75% of the participants could complete their markers quickly, suggesting that while the material was initially confusing, they could swiftly adapt and apply their creative skills to overcome the difficulties (see Figure 5).

4.2.2 Decision-Making and Selection Pressure. The activity revealed that participants experienced considerable decision-making pressure when selecting colours and pieces, particularly when working with LEGO® bricks in the second workshop. This pressure stemmed from the wide range of options available and the need to make choices directly influencing their creations' outcomes. The open-ended nature of LEGO®, which allows for endless combinations and constructions, likely contributed to the participants' heightened sense of responsibility and care in their selections. The data shows that 87.5% of the participants (seven out of eight) encountered decision-making pressure during this selection phase, indicating a widespread impact on their interaction with the materials. This high percentage reveals that the selection process was a critical component of the activity, influencing how the students engaged with the task and how they felt about their creative decisions. The following conversation between ID7 and the facilitator gives an example:

ID7: *I couldn't decide which bricks and colours to pick to make the necklace there were just so many options on the table.*

Facilitator: *How did you complete the necklace then?*

ID7: *I mean, I was the last one to finish. I think I spent all my time finding yellow LEGO®, but then I also wanted two small purple coins to put as gems on the necklace.*

Facilitator: *Were you happy with the necklace you made?*

ID7: *I guess so, but I think I was more stressed about deciding what colours and shapes I needed to pick, and I didn't realise I got lost in finding it and wasted all my time.*

Fig. 4: The left image, featuring raindrops, represents participants' preference for simplicity as six recreated a straightforward version of the raincoat. The right image, showing a lock, symbolises the shift to abstract thinking, as participants explored diverse and metaphorical representations for the diary.

Fig. 5: Markers created by children using different materials in the second workshop, displayed from left to right: "Whiteboard," "Puzzle pieces," "LEGO® bricks," and "Foam blocks." The markers are arranged in the order of their creation, illustrating the progression of the children's designs and thought processes using these materials.

Seven out of eight participants took approximately 5-8 minutes to decide on the colours and pieces they would use. To give two further examples; ID9 spent the most time gathering black and grey LEGO® bricks to create their marker (see Figure 6, left). Meanwhile, ID13 struggled to finish their marker as they wanted yellow round LEGO® bricks to signify coins for their markers (see Figure 6, right). This extended decision-making period highlights the internal deliberations each participant engaged in as they considered the functional aspects of the pieces and their aesthetic and symbolic value. The fact that nearly all participants experienced this pressure underscores the intensity of the decision-making process in creative activities involving open-ended materials like LEGO®. It also suggests that the participants were acutely aware of the importance of their choices, leading them to invest considerable time and thought into the selection process.

4.2.3 Collaboration and Social Connection. Collaboration and social connection emerged as crucial behaviours among participants during the activity, particularly when encountering difficulties (see Figure 7). Faced with unfamiliar materials such as foam blocks and puzzle pieces, participants frequently sought help from their peers, demonstrating a strong reliance on social interaction to overcome challenges. An example of this collaborative behaviour was

observed when participants struggled to manipulate the new materials. The complexities of shaping foam blocks and puzzle pieces into the required forms often led to confusion and uncertainty. In response, many participants instinctively sought guidance from their peers, asking for tips on handling the materials better or approaching the task. This exchange of ideas and strategies helped individual participants progress and fostered a collective problem-solving environment. Additionally, the collaborative spirit extended to other aspects of the activity, such as when students were tasked with creating stories and markers in pairs. Working together allowed them to pool their cognitive resources, leading to more creative and effective outcomes. 50% of the participants preferred to work in pairs when creating markers, emphasising the role of collaboration in their learning process. For example, they noted:

My friends sitting next to me helped me make it. (ID9)

I didn't know how to complete my object and then [ID10] gave me extra LEGO® bricks, and we completed it together; that was so much fun. (ID14)

By working together, participants could share ideas, offer feedback, and support each other's learning, resulting in a richer and more dynamic educational experience.

Fig. 6: Participants interacted with various materials, highlighting their decision-making processes. ID9 focused on searching for black bricks (left), while ID13 spent considerable time looking for yellow bricks (right).

Fig. 7: Moments from Workshop 2, capturing participants actively collaborating and engaging in social interactions during the marker creation process. The images depict lively discussions as participants shared tips (left), offered assistance (right), and worked together, fostering an environment of active peer learning and mutual support.

4.2.4 Material Preferences and Feedback. During the activity, participants displayed distinct preferences for certain materials, largely influenced by their ease of use and potential for creative expression. These preferences highlighted how individual comfort and the perceived creative possibilities of a material can impact a participant's engagement and enjoyment. For example, foam blocks emerged as a favourite among four participants due to their soft texture, making them enjoyable and challenging to manipulate. The tactile comfort provided by the foam blocks allowed the participants to focus more on their creativity, leading them to explore various ways to shape and combine the material. The foam blocks, in particular, were favoured by half of the participants, with four out of eight students selecting it as their preferred medium. These participants appreciated the material's physical softness and the challenge it presented in construction. The ability to quickly adapt and experiment with the foam blocks allowed them to create various shapes, which likely contributed to its popularity. For example, ID11 said that *the foam was so so soft, I kept hugging it and then I took more foam and made 3 newspapers because I wanted to play more. I think*

that was the best one compared to all the other ones that I played with. It was easier to figure out how to make the newspaper with foam than with anything else. Or ID10 noted that *I liked foam the best, it was not plastic. It was big and soft.*

On the other hand, two participants preferred the puzzle pieces, valuing their flexibility in forming both 2D and 3D structures. The versatility of puzzle pieces offered these participants a broader range of creative possibilities, particularly for those who enjoyed experimenting with dimensions and forms. For example, ID8 highlighted *I wanted to play with puzzles more and more. You know I made two purses with different colours and it made me so happy.*

This preference contrast between foam blocks and puzzle pieces illustrates how different materials can cater to diverse creative approaches and comfort levels. The data from the activity further highlights these varied material preferences. With 50% of the participants (four out of eight) indicating a preference for foam blocks, it is clear that this material resonated with most of the group, likely due to its balance of challenge and comfort. Meanwhile, 25% of

the participants (two out of eight) preferred puzzle pieces, emphasising the appeal of materials that offer flexibility and the potential for more complex creations. Surprisingly, only one participant preferred LEGO® bricks, while the other preferred drawing on a whiteboard.

4.3 Balancing Creativity and Usability in MAR Interactive Marker Design

This section explores the feasibility and functionality of prototypes created by children and compares them with the feasibility suggested by designers. The analysis highlights the tension between creative abstraction and practical constraints, considering these markers' reproducibility and, recognisability.

Out of the 48 prototypes made by participants, we identified 22 as the most feasible for inclusion in Mobile AR games. The following sections present the criteria used to evaluate the prototypes.

4.3.1 Balancing Creativity with Practical Constraints. Creativity in marker design plays a crucial role in engaging users and enhancing the MAR game experience. However, unrestrained creativity often leads to practical challenges. One key challenge in evaluating the feasibility of interactive markers was addressing the subjective nature of some participants' creative ideas. Prototypes that leaned heavily on abstract or highly personalised interpretations of objects, such as ID7's newspaper soaked in water or ID13's book made from LEGO® bricks (see Figure 8), highlighted an intriguing balance between creativity and practicality in marker design. These designs were undoubtedly inventive and showcased the participants' imaginative engagement with the task. For instance, ID7's soaked newspaper was a visually distinct marker, pushing the boundaries of conventional design by incorporating unusual forms like the use of water to interpret newspaper. Similarly, ID13's LEGO® book introduced a playful, modular interpretation of a book that could be opened from all sides.

However, these creative approaches also introduce practical challenges, particularly concerning reproducibility and usability. ID7's soaked newspaper, while distinctive, raises concerns about its interpretation for a wider user group. The impermanent nature of the marker could lead to inconsistencies in marker functionality over time and across users. Similarly, while visually compelling, ID13's LEGO® book requires specific LEGO® bricks, limiting its reproducibility and scalability for broader audiences. These examples underscore the tension between fostering creativity and ensuring feasibility in marker design. While such designs can enhance user engagement and provide unique, memorable experiences, they must also be evaluated for their ability to meet MAR gameplay's technical and logistical demands. Achieving this balance is crucial to integrating creative prototypes into practical and accessible interactive marker games.

4.3.2 Reproducibility. Reproducibility is another crucial consideration when evaluating the feasibility of prototypes for MAR games. A marker's ability to be consistently recreated across different settings ensures technical viability and usability in diverse contexts. Among the prototypes, the simplicity and clarity of certain prototypes made them highly reproducible. For instance, ID8's math symbol, created on a whiteboard, and ID12's LEGO® bricks purse

were remarkable (see Figure 9). Their straightforward structures, lack of dependency on intricate details or specific colours, and ease of construction make them suitable for widespread use. Furthermore, ID8 proposed incorporating a riddle into gameplay, hinting at a math symbol as the answer, adding an engaging layer of interactivity while reinforcing the marker's reproducibility.

In contrast, more complex designs, such as ID8's 3D pen with puzzles or ID14's 3D receipt maker pose challenges (see Figure 10). These prototypes highlight issues with scalability and consistency due to their three-dimensional nature, which proved less accessible for participants. We observed that over 50% of participants preferred building 2D prototypes over 3D ones, underscoring the need for markers to cater to diverse skill levels. This observation further emphasised that while artistic complexity can enhance creativity, it must be balanced with practical considerations to ensure consistent reproduction.

4.3.3 Recognisability. Recognisability is critical in ensuring the AR system accurately identifies markers without errors, essential for seamless user experiences in MAR games. Clear, distinct features—such as bold shapes, simple colours, and universally familiar symbols—help to minimise the likelihood of misidentification by the AR tracking software. For instance, a trapezium marker crafted by ID10 using foam blocks stood out for its straightforward geometry and visual simplicity (see Figure 11, left). The foam material's adaptability and the trapezium's bold shape ensure it can be easily recognisable by the AR software and reproducible by other users with minimal variation. Similarly, a necklace prototype created by ID14 using puzzle pieces showcased an effective balance of visual clarity and functionality (see Figure 11, right). Its recognisable form and the thoughtful arrangement of puzzle pieces can allow the prototype to maintain high accuracy in AR recognition. Markers like these demonstrate the feasibility of designs that balance creativity and practicality. By adhering to universally understandable shapes and patterns, these prototypes can maintain functionality while reducing the likelihood of errors in AR tracking detection. Despite their creative origins, these prototypes highlight the importance of adhering to universally understandable shapes and patterns. Such prototypes can reduce the cognitive load on users and the technical demands on AR tracking systems, allowing for smoother interactions. Additionally, markers with high recognisability, like ID10's trapezium and ID14's necklace, align with the technical requirements of AR while being reproducible by varied users with minimal customisation.

5 Discussions

This section compares designers' preferences with children's actual interactions with marker materials, highlighting their impact on engagement and immersion in MAR games. Balancing innovation with accessibility is key to fostering creativity while ensuring materials enhance, rather than hinder, educational and entertainment outcomes.

5.1 RQ 1 - Key Considerations of Designers

The designers' approach to selecting materials for interactive markers in MAR games reveals a crucial balance between practical functionality and user engagement. Instead of focusing primarily on

Fig. 8: Prototypes created by participants: On the left, ID7 crafted a newspaper soaked in water, using a whiteboard as the material to represent their idea of a newspaper. Similarly, ID13 showcased a talking book, complete with googly eyes that open from all sides, constructed using LEGO® bricks to represent their concept of a book.

Fig. 9: Prototypes created by participants: On the left, ID8 designed a math symbol using geometric shapes on a whiteboard to represent their concept of a math book. On the right, ID12 constructed a LEGO® purse using basic bricks in a simple structure.

Fig. 10: Prototypes created by participants: On the left, ID8 created a complex 3D pen structure using yellow and purple puzzles to metaphorically represent a book. Similarly, ID14 created a 3D receipt maker on the right using foam pieces and some blocks on the side to show receipts.

Fig. 11: On the left, ID10 designed a simple trapezium shape using basic foam blocks to represent a math book, emphasizing simplicity and clarity. ID14 crafted a necklace prototype on the right using yellow and purple puzzle pieces, creating a visually distinct and modular design.

technological efficiency in AR material design, designers emphasised the importance of performance and creative expression. This dual focus aligns with design literature [72], highlighting the user-driven exploration for innovative outcomes.

5.1.1 Preference for Everyday and Sustainable Materials. The designers' inclination towards everyday, recyclable materials reflects the growing trend in sustainable design. Like Ljungberg's [44] findings on user preferences for accessible, low-cost resources, our designers frequently mentioned using materials such as paper, seashells, and dice. These materials merge accessibility with creativity, with seashells, for instance, introducing an organic aesthetic that enhances user engagement—a concept supported by sensory design research [67]. This choice to repurpose materials also resonates with the increasing importance of environmental sustainability, linking creative expression with ecological responsibility.

5.1.2 Versatility and Customisation in Material Choices. Designers placed a high value on physical objects that offer versatility and customisation, supporting previous research on flexible, user-modifiable tools in interactive design [33]. Materials like LEGO® bricks, clay, and 3D puzzles were favoured for their modularity and adaptability. Discussions around LEGO®, in particular, highlighted its collaborative, dynamic potential, which aligns with LeGoff et al.'s [40] research showing the social skill benefits of modular play. However, the participants acknowledged the technical challenges of translating these materials into consistently recognisable MAR markers, particularly with surfaces like clay that can hinder AR recognition [42].

5.1.3 Visual Design and Challenges with AR Recognition. The designers' focus on colour and patterns highlights the importance of visual salience in marker design. Vibrant colours and intricate patterns ensured that markers stood out and remained engaging. This aligns with Ferrer et al.'s [19] research on the role of colour and contrast in enhancing user interfaces. However, while these materials support creative freedom, they pose technical challenges in MAR environments. For instance, while clay enables detailed

designs, its surface variability complicates accurate recognition—a common issue in marker-based AR systems.

To balance creative freedom with technical reliability, designers should explore hybrid materials that combine organic elements with more stable, MAR-compatible components. Further research should also focus on developing methods to improve MAR recognition for adaptable materials like clay and 3D puzzles. Optimising using colours and geometric patterns to enhance marker recognition across diverse environments is crucial for sustaining visual engagement while meeting technical requirements. Our findings highlight the intersection between designers' creative aspirations and the technical challenges inherent in MAR marker design. While everyday materials offer sustainability and creative potential, MAR systems require advancements to support their reliable recognition. Future MAR applications must bridge the gap between creativity and functionality, ensuring that interactive marker designs engage users and perform consistently within technical constraints. Continued research is essential to refining these materials, leading to more effective, inclusive, and sustainable MAR experiences.

5.2 RQ 2 - Interactions Exhibited by Children

The first workshop revealed MAR gaming's potential and challenges for new users. While seven of eight participants found it engaging, technical difficulties highlighted the need for clearer instructions and built-in guidance. Despite initial reliance on facilitators, AR's blend of physical and digital interaction fostered engagement and creativity. Participants progressed from literal to abstract marker designs, balancing functionality and symbolism.

In Workshop 2, children collaborated on storytelling, strengthening social connections. Their interactions with new materials provided insights into adaptability, creativity, and peer collaboration, reinforcing research on design thinking and social learning. Their strategies for overcoming material challenges and decision-making pressure highlight how children navigate creative problem-solving in unfamiliar contexts.

5.2.1 Initial Struggles and Adaptability. Participants initially hesitated and were uncertain when new materials like puzzles and

foam were introduced. The facilitators maintained an observational role, offering assistance only if the participants explicitly requested it. Without any direct involvement of the facilitators, participants explored the materials independently, and their process naturally adapted in response to the initial challenges they faced. This mirrors existing research on children's adaptability and creative problem-solving, where uncertainty and confusion are considered necessary stages in the decision-making process [15, 70]. The participants' experience aligns with the concept of "iterative design," as many restarted their projects after gaining familiarity with the materials, illustrating their shift from confusion to experimentation [72]. Given time and flexibility, this process underscores how children can overcome initial barriers to engage deeply with creative tasks.

5.2.2 Decision-Making Pressure and Open-Ended Creativity. Participants experienced decision-making pressure, particularly when choosing colours and pieces while working with LEGO® bricks. This tension between creativity and the abundance of choices reflects research on decision fatigue, where too many options can overwhelm the decision-making process [19]. Participants often spent extended time (5-8 minutes) deliberating on their selections, which aligns with the research by Li et al.[42] on the paralysis of choice in creative environments. This suggests that managing decision-making pressure is crucial in maintaining engagement and creativity.

5.2.3 Collaboration and Social Connection. Collaboration emerged as a critical strategy for participants to overcome material challenges, especially with complex materials like puzzles and foam. This supports socio-constructivist learning theories, which emphasise the importance of social interaction in creative tasks, especially in MAR games [48]. Participants frequently sought help from their peers, reflecting the value of cooperative problem-solving. These collaborative efforts not only helped the children navigate material challenges but also fostered social connections as they worked together, shared ideas, and supported each other in achieving common goals. Such interactions contribute to a sense of belonging and community, further enhancing the social connection aspects of the activity. Additionally, material preferences—such as the popularity of foam—highlight how comfort and ease of use can influence creative engagement, supported by research on haptic learning shows that tactile, physically engaging materials enhance cognitive engagement [76].

These findings have important implications for designing educational environments that foster creativity and problem-solving. Researchers and educators should introduce tools gradually to help children adapt to unfamiliar materials and provide scaffolding to build confidence. Balancing open-ended creativity with structured guidance can reduce decision-making pressure and enhance creative expression. Encouraging peer collaboration fosters social learning, problem-solving and meaningful social connections, as children work together, share ideas, and support each other's efforts. By promoting collaboration, educators can also strengthen interpersonal bonds, which enhance students' social-emotional development. Offering diverse materials catering to sensory preferences ensures students can choose tools that suit their comfort and creative needs. Ultimately, designing flexible, inclusive environments with various materials can create more dynamic and effective

learning experiences, allowing children to engage fully with their cognitive and creative potential.

5.3 RQ 3 - Designers' Expectations versus Children's Behaviour

Our goal was to understand how designers' expectations of effective marker materials compare to children's actual preferences and behaviours when interacting with those materials. By analysing both perspectives on how these two groups approach material selection, we aimed to explore the gap between the creative and functional intentions of designers and the practical engagement of children.

While designers expressed interest in exploring recyclable and versatile materials, the prototypes highlighted a divergence between conceptual aspirations and practical usability. For instance, the designers valued the potential of clay for its customisability but acknowledged its limitations in terms of consistent marker recognition. However, participants' overly imaginative prototypes, like ID7's soaked newspaper and ID13's LEGO® book, highlight children's tendency to push conventional boundaries by incorporating unconventional materials and forms. While these approaches reveal a rich depth of creativity and personal expression, they also pose technical feasibility and reproducibility challenges, often exceeding the designers' anticipated constraints. Therefore, simpler designs using foam blocks or whiteboards can prove to align more closely with the technical requirements and ease of use envisioned by the designers. This divergence suggests a fundamental difference in focus: while designers prioritise technical and practical considerations, children lean toward playful and narrative-driven engagement.

On the other hand, while the participants were drawn to soft and tactile materials like foam for ease of use, their experiences showed initial struggles with unfamiliar materials, particularly puzzles and foam. Children needed time to adapt, but they displayed creativity and adaptability once comfortable. Their decision-making process often involved pressure, especially when given too many choices, sometimes hindering their engagement. These behaviours underscore the importance of balancing the creative freedom afforded to children with structured guidance that steers their imagination toward feasible outcomes. Designers can leverage this insight by framing design tasks to align with children's natural inclinations toward narrative and personalisation while maintaining technical boundaries.

Social interaction played a critical role, as children frequently sought peer collaboration to overcome challenges, highlighting the importance of cooperative problem-solving in their engagement with materials. Materials like LEGO® bricks and puzzles supported collaboration and experimentation, fostering a sense of social connection as children worked together to build and create. This collaborative approach allowed participants to share ideas, negotiate solutions, and build on each other's creativity, reinforcing the idea that social interaction is integral to learning and development. Such interactions also helped strengthen bonds between peers, fostering a sense of community and belonging within the group. These findings align with the designers' goal of encouraging interactive and shared MAR experiences, where teamwork and communication

are essential components of gameplay. The prototypes highlighted how such materials can balance technical constraints and creative freedom. Foam blocks emerged as a favourite due to their balance of tactile comfort and creative potential, challenging the designers to rethink their emphasis on less intuitive materials. Similarly, whiteboard designs underscored the value of simplicity in enabling dynamic and user-friendly interactions. These social interactions were not just about solving material-related challenges but also about creating meaningful connections and reinforcing the social-emotional aspects of the learning process.

We, therefore, identify the following design challenges for the HCI and design community when aligning designer expectations with user preferences:

- How can we design marker materials that balance designers' creative aspirations with the technical demands of MAR environments, ensuring creativity and reliable marker recognition?
- How do we design materials that allow for open-ended creativity while minimising decision-making fatigue and ensuring children feel supported in their choices?
- How can we integrate collaborative and socially supportive mechanisms into MAR game design to foster peer interaction and problem-solving among young users?

This study highlights the importance of bridging the gap between designer expectations and user preferences in material selection for MAR games. The insights gained call for thoughtful material design that supports creativity and technical functionality, ensuring that MAR environments cater to both designers' goals and children's dynamic and social engagement. Our qualitative analysis of designer interviews and children's workshops revealed five factors critical to material selection for interactive markers in MAR games:

- (1) **Simplification:** Limiting the number of options for colours, shapes, or components reduces decision-making fatigue, helping participants focus on creative exploration rather than being overwhelmed by choices.
- (2) **Customisation:** The more modular and flexible the materials are, the easier it is for users to create and modify dynamic structures that adapt to various design scenarios.
- (3) **Sustainability:** Prioritise recyclable and environmentally friendly materials to balance creativity with sustainable design practices.
- (4) **Balanced creativity:** Providing a mix of open-ended creativity with structured tasks can maintain engagement while preventing creative paralysis, enabling users to feel inspired yet focused.
- (5) **Collaboration:** Selecting materials that encourage teamwork, such as modular puzzles or LEGO®, enhances social interaction and fosters a shared sense of accomplishment among participants.

5.4 Reflection of the Methods

A considerable strength of the co-design methodology was its ability to accommodate diverse participant groups i.e. designers and children, by tailoring activities to their expertise and perspective. The use of a multi-phase approach, involving interviews, initial exploratory activities, and iterative prototyping, allowed for a layered

understanding of both material selection criteria and user interaction patterns. This structure ensured that insights from one stage informed subsequent phases, enhancing the overall coherence of the study. One notable aspect of the methodology was its reliance on low-fidelity prototyping, which emphasised creativity over technical implementations. Additionally, it offered the ability to prototype for technologies that are either not yet available or fully developed [11]. Furthermore, this method encouraged children to provide honest and insightful feedback [62], enabling designers to make more informed decisions and potentially saving development time in creating MAR games. This approach effectively highlighted how participants adapted to and interacted with familiar and unfamiliar materials.

In alignment with discussions on onboarding and comprehension in user involvement, as highlighted by Saiger et al. [57], the methodology incorporated a foundational phase to introduce participants to AR concepts through Workshop 1. By employing activities like re-drawing game markers on whiteboards, the method effectively reinforced key AR principles and established a shared vocabulary, such as "markers," enabling deeper engagement in the second workshop. Workshop 2, structured into collaborative pair work and individual tasks, was designed to balance collective dialogue with independent creativity. While effective in generating diverse ideas, this approach exposed limitations highlighting power imbalances in group dynamics. Consistent with the work of Hourcade et al. [29], familiar groupings sometimes led to dominant voices overshadowing quieter participants, highlighting the need for facilitation techniques that mitigate power imbalances. The adaptability of the methodology was evident, however, as most participants engaged productively, leveraging the "magic machine" method [2] to explore complex social issues. The open-ended method encouraged creativity but posed challenges. Two participants initially took the task lightly, while two others finished quickly and distracted others. One participant struggled to complete their prototype due to surrounding distractions and indecision over materials. Despite this, the reflective discussions at the end showcased meaningful contributions from all participants. Lastly, an area of reflection is the impact of time constraints. While the staged approach supported incremental learning, the limited workshop duration hindered deeper exploration and idea development. Delays in onboarding and a break disrupted the flow of activities, requiring additional time to re-engage the participants. These constraints reduced the depth of observations and discussions, limiting the potential for richer qualitative insights. Extending the workshop could foster richer insights into participant behaviors and the design process's impact.

5.5 Limitations

In the first half of the interview, designers faced technical issues such as internet connectivity problems, software glitches, and communication delays. These disruptions interrupted the flow of discussion, making it harder for designers to maintain focus and momentum. We believe these challenges may have impacted their ability to engage fully with the brainstorming process. Additionally, the collaborative nature of brainstorming often involves real-time sketching and prototyping, which designers typically rely on to

express and build upon ideas. However, since the session was conducted online, it was difficult to replicate the spontaneity and fluidity of in-person collaboration. The absence of immediate access to physical materials and real-time sketching likely limited their ability to communicate and refine their ideas effectively.

In the Workshop 1, participants were introduced to a MAR game to help them become familiar with the mechanics and experience of MAR gaming. We suspect their exposure to this game influenced their creative decisions in Workshop 2, where they were tasked with developing their own MAR game storylines. It is possible that their story creations were shaped by the game they had played earlier, introducing a potential bias in their narrative development. Lastly, our participants were clearly restricted by the requirement for English proficiency and the 10–14-year age bracket. Research involving other age groups without language restrictions might offer a substantially distinctive perspective, potentially resulting in varied outcomes in this analysis.

5.6 Future Work

With this study, we open new perspectives for a wide range of future work in the realm of interactive 2D and 3D markers and empirical approaches to marker selection while designing MAR games. While the present work is a starting point for understanding how users interact with these markers, we envision future research focused on developing a working prototype based on our findings. This prototype will serve as the basis for workshops with the same participants, allowing us to analyse and compare their behaviours in the study with their interactions within the game environment. Since interactive markers are an emerging study area, future directions should include exploring advanced AR technologies that enable seamless 3D object recognition in the physical environment. This will enhance the realism and interactivity of AR games, pushing the boundaries of how players engage with the digital and physical worlds. We also see opportunities to explore new methods for researching interactive markers, encouraging scholars to adopt approaches that better capture the details of user interactions in AR settings.

Finally, we call on the research community to involve a broader range of participants, moving beyond convenience sampling to include diverse and hard-to-reach populations. This will ensure a more comprehensive understanding of how different user groups engage with interactive markers in MAR games, ultimately contributing to developing more inclusive and effective AR experiences.

6 Conclusion

We have conducted online interviews with designers (N=6) and two interactive workshops with children (N=8) to understand their perspectives on material selection for interactive markers in MAR games. By examining the designers' preferences and the children's interaction strategies, we have identified key considerations for marker materials that balance functionality, creativity, and user engagement. The key takeaways from this study highlight the critical factors for designing interactive materials in MAR games: simplification to reduce decision fatigue, customisation for creative flexibility, sustainability for long-term usability, balanced creativity

to maintain engagement, and collaboration to foster social interaction. These considerations provide valuable guidance for creating more intuitive and engaging MAR experiences. We discussed the implications of these findings for MAR game design, highlighting the importance of aligning material choices with user needs to enhance gameplay experiences. We also reflect on children's challenges when interacting with unfamiliar materials, suggesting that design strategies should accommodate diverse user behaviours. Our study opens new avenues for future research on integrating user-centred design practices in selecting interactive materials for MAR games.

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